

THE PROCESS OF CREATING A CINEMATOGRAPHIC WORK

Film (production)

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Durim Kryeziu

University of Prishtina “Hasan Prishtina” Faculty of Arts.
Department of Film Directing, Republic of Kosova.

Abstract

The study aims to address the issue presented with the title of the work, the process of creating a cinematographic work. The issue is addressed in the practical and professional aspect of the production of a cinematographic work. In this case, based on my practical experience, professional and international scientific literature from the field of cinematography I have analyzed the process in details starting with finding of the idea, finding of the budget, finding of the creative and technical team, adequate preparation for the recording, assembly and distribution of the film to the general public.

Introduction

The creation of a cinematic work requires a great commitment going through stages from finding the idea, buying copyright for adaptation from dramas or various writings, finding the necessary budgets from various private and public funds, employment of the artistic and technical team who must remain loyal to the work from the beginning to the end by assisting in the preparation and then on adequate terrains.¹

Collaborations and the chain link between many sectors is a key element in the realization of a cinematographic work by working on long hours, weeks and depending on the work even for months.² Image and audio recording in co-ordination with actors on a stage is very important. It is a link and creation of a chronological timeline by creating a particular story or content. Distribution is of great importance to a work because it will enable it to be seen for a wider public by appearing in cinemas and TV platforms and modern methods of the time.

Development

To create a cinematographic work the first thing one needs to possess is *the idea*. So the idea is the starting point for everything. Ideas move around you. The idea may be original as the script writer sees from the actions and behaviors of people in real life, as well as the idea may arise from real event that can be a very good foundation but that also needs to be met or adapted for the film narration by developing the intrigue, the characters, the dialogue, and so on. But more and more is used the original narration which is being written just for the movie since it is cheaper and

¹ Filmmaker manual: how to write and make a short film - Andrea Nobile, Viola Rispoli, Andrea Tarquini, pp. 91

² Paul Martingell - Better Location Shooting - Techniques For Video Production, pp. 20

costs are smaller and it is more feasible, more communicative and it deals with human problems that the characters have among themselves.

While the adaptation of a literary work depends on the success of the work: the greater the success, the higher is the cost. In addition to the cost, film studios are also influenced by the competition, and they raise the price to a very high degree. To this must be added the amount to be paid for film adaptation of the novel or drama.

The other element is the development of the idea. So this element is important for the development of the idea because it deals with research of the causes that have led a character to do an action. After finding the idea, the screenwriter needs to create situations, characters, an ironic turning-point, how to end the story, is it necessary that the material becomes a sketch.

Another important step is to write the synopsis, in which the names of characters, age, profession, the main conflict must have a dramatic flow with dramaturgical turning-points and an epilogue, the synopsis should be clear and concrete, not to be poetic, but to tell the main events in the film.

The next step behind the synopsis is the treatment where the story about the film is going to be more extensive, stumbling across all the characters, histories, conflicts among the characters, confrontations and controversies, in the treatment we must understand the geographic and time element of the plot by giving detailed elements about the film story.³

The process of completing the script is of great importance to the producer because he does an analysis of how to manage the film's realization and financing. So he plans to finance its realization, finding adequate funds, and earning profits after the film's realization.⁴

We have two forms of budget completeness: the first is private film funding and the receipt of private funds and the public. By completing the budget, producers and screenwriters ask potential filmmakers to realize the film work.

Pre-production

Finding the right director is one of the first things to do. Producer in collaboration with the director chooses the artistic and technical team of the film. With the choice of the main people, the work starts in different sectors, such as scattering the script, separating it into locations, then comes the scene, drawing scenarios, extracting requisites, collecting numbers, selecting the scene finder begins finding of the most appropriate locations based on the time of the event that is

³ Writing - Directing and Producing Documentary Films and Videos – Third edition – Alan Rosenthal. P.14

⁴ Bastian Cleve - Film Production Management. P.12

written in the script, parallel work is also the opening of the auditions and the selection of appropriate actors for the main, secondary, episodic and figurative roles that will be involved in a cinematographic work.

When designing the costume designer, it will be done the finding and the sewing of the appropriate costumes. The director selects the director of photography and based on the locations, artistic and aesthetic findings are done on how to record the film, how the movie colors will look like, with what technical equipment will be recording it such as cameras, lenses, light and technical equipment that will be of service during movie recording. At this stage everything needs to be done, everyone who is in the team should be contracted; planning must be done for each run. It is a final stage that can be done in the office.

Production

Based on the planning that has been done earlier this phase follows what has been done earlier. Recording in a film frame is done after each member of the team at the recording spot. Cinema is a history story in images. So the director is the one who should have clearly visualized the story by explaining to the staff how and what to record.⁵

The first person to go in place of the recording is the location manager who will take care of the arrival of the team and provide parking, then assistant director and other staff. Then the actors come because they have to be dressed up, wear costumes and put grime on actors.

With the arrival of the director, the actors must come to make the first proofs. With the camera and the lights set up, the creative process and recording of the cadres where the analysis of all sectors is done, making careful analysis of the recording angles and the actions of the actors.

The director assistant should inform the whole team about the next cadres to be rolled out. He calls for silence. When all are in silence the assistant called for the toner who gives a verbal signal, then the camera section, in front of the camera is a table showing the number of the scene and the cadre being read and closed. After silence the director says "action" to start the actor's actions within the film framework and then the assistant gives a greater signal to the whole team.

At the end of the day, the director approves tomorrow's filming schedule and a daily report of progress is sent to the production office. This includes the days of the day plan, the progression of scenes, audio files, and record quads. Callouts are distributed to all staff to show them when and where to record the next day.

⁵ Filmmaker manual: how to write and make a short film - Andrea Nobile, Viola Rispoli, Andrea Tarquini, p. 60.

Heads of departments with the director in charge gather to see and discuss the materials that were filmed earlier. Continuity is another important element of the movie filming process because the film is not filmed in chronology as the film will be filmed in the final production but will be filmed as a mosaic while preserving the style, logic, visual aspects, the actors' play that at the stage of the montage when creating the connection of the scenes the spectator will create a harmonic whole by creating the link of the story and its meaning.

Continuity is another element that needs to be taken into account because often it takes a lot of days to record anywhere from 30 to 35 days, then with hours around 14 or 18 hours in remote locations, film production in the field tends to create a team spirit. When the film finishes, recording is usually organized to thank the entire film crew.⁶

After the end of the recording, the whole team goes to rest, especially the director relaxes, creates a distance from the record material, gets new physical and psychic energies because it is now the main stage when a lot of work at different stages or the record materials in pieces will be bound to create a wholesome piece.⁷

Along with the new member of the team, a montager does the synchronization between audio and video. On the basis of letters of continuity, the selection of the best quadrants is made. At this stage there are hours and days in a room that will look like a prison cell. The montage will create the story rhythm using creativity, extracting tonal elements, and correcting eventual mistakes that occurred during filmmaking because at the end of the film, the audience sees the mounted and non-recorded material. If the recorded material is the body of the film, then the montage is the Spirit. The ultimate editing draft is when there is a ranking of plans giving a chronological sense, giving direction to the story from the beginning to the end, so an event occurs, then another, then another till the resolution of the story.

The director's work has already been accomplished from this moment by several other people to finalize the cinematographic work. Sound engineer will be engaged in his studio to clean up the sound of noise, level up the dialogue voice, put the tonic effect on demand, based on needs he call the actors in the studio to rearrange the dialogues. At the same time this work is done by correcting and painting the film to give the atmosphere and the appropriate colors, at this stage in the studio, the color artist works together with the director and the director of photography.⁸

In parallel, the composer works together with the instrumentalists to give the music a sense of emotion to adequate scenes. When all the creative works in different sectors are supposed to finish, the material will have to be matched and the composer together with the director will harmonize all the works of the sectors by attaching the graphics and getting ready to export the

⁶ The Technique of Film and Video Editing – History, Theory, and Practice Fifth Edition by Ken Dancyger, p. 380.

⁷ Nicholas Proferes - Film Directing Fundamentals See Your Film Before Shooting, p. 154.

⁸ The Technique of Film and Video Editing – History, Theory, and Practice Fifth Edition by Ken Dancyger, p. 380

project. Project exportation implies completion of the project as a creative, short and technical process, then tests it on the appropriate cinemas and with the latest suggestions the final export is completed by completing the project.

Distribution

Film distribution starts with application at the festival, which is a great opportunity to present the cinematographic work. This stage requires some engagements such as crossing on a red carpet, interviews with journalists, tours, or main body tours to present to the public and conversation that is made by sharing public reviews about the movie. Playing at the cinema will be a great opportunity to watch the film and producers to get their costs off. Film distribution can also be made through (VHS, VCD, DVD, Blu-ray) or can be downloaded directly from any website or you can see it on a landing platform where you can rent, pay-per-view, VOD, cable, satellite or free broadcasting. At the end, major distribution agencies list the best and most interesting movies that the audience can enjoy by distributing them all over the world. The whole work is analyzed and interpreted with the theme of the process of creating a cinematographic work.

In this modest work based on my experience as a director, screenwriter, producer and assistant at the university I have managed to analyze in details the main production processes of a cinematographic work such as: development, pre-production, production, post-production and distribution. In conclusion, we can say that we have chronologically analyzed the work in question.

References

1. Cleve, B. Film Production Management., p. 12.
2. Filmmaker manual: how to write and make a short film - Andrea Nobile, Viola Rispoli, Andrea Tarquini, p. 60.
3. Filmmaker manual: How to write and make a short film - Andrea Nobile, Viola Rispoli, Andrea Tarquini, p. 91.
4. Proferes, N. Film Directing Fundamentals See Your Film Before Shooting, p. 154.
5. Martingell, P. Better Location Shooting - Techniques For Video Production, p. 20.
6. The Insider's Guide to Independent Film Distribution - Stacey Parks, p.75.
7. The Technique of Film and Video Editing – History, Theory, and Practice Fifth Edition by Ken Dancyger, p. 380.
8. Writing - Directing and Producing Documentary Films and Videos – Third edition – Alan Rosenthal, p. 14.